

Quantum Mechanics as Observer-Induced Quotient Graph Dynamics

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Abstract

We propose a discrete ontological reconstruction of quantum mechanics based on a graph-theoretic model with deterministic cyclic dynamics. The model is founded on the hypothesis that quantum mechanics is an effective description of reality from the perspective of an internal observer, that is, an observer who is part of the finite system (world) being observed.

A central element of the model is the principle of subjective incompleteness: in general, the set of states of the system (ontological states) exceeds the set of observable states and cannot be fully distinguished by the internal observer. This leads to taking the quotient of the set of ontological states with respect to indistinguishability and naturally induces a probabilistic structure in which probabilities are determined by the cardinalities of the corresponding equivalence classes.

It is shown that the cyclic structure of the dynamics, combined with this quotient construction, leads to the emergence of complex amplitudes and the Born rule. Thus, the formalism of quantum mechanics arises as an effective description of deterministic dynamics after quotienting.

It is further shown that the geometry of the edge space of a complete graph realizes a discrete phase space with an action of the Heisenberg–Weyl group, and that in the continuum limit the model leads to the Klein–Gordon equation.

Within this approach, the structure of quantum mechanics appears as a representational level of description of the quotient cyclic dynamics.

Introduction

Quantum mechanics (QM) is extremely successful as a predictive theory; however, the physical meaning of its mathematical structure remains the subject of ongoing discussions. In particular, fundamental questions concern the role of complex amplitudes, global phase symmetry, and the status of the Born rule. This motivates the search for constructive models that may clarify whether quantum behavior is fundamental or arises as an effective description of a deeper level of dynamics.

The approach considered in this work is inspired by the ideas of Everett and Wheeler, who proposed incorporating the observer into physical theory [1,2]. This line of thought is currently represented, in particular, by Rovelli's relational quantum mechanics [3] and quantum Bayesianism (QBism) [4]. A common feature of these approaches is that quantum theory is viewed as a description of physical reality from the perspective of an observer who is part of the system.

In this work, we propose a formalism based on a graph-theoretic model of the world with an internal observer. By an internal observer we mean an abstract, idealized observer whose states are identified with observable physical states.

In the model, observable states are represented by the vertices of a directed graph, while the edges correspond to possible transitions between them and form the set of ontological states. At the

fundamental level, the dynamics is deterministic and is realized in the form of cycles on the set of edges.

A central element of the model is the principle of subjective incompleteness: the set of ontological states cannot be put into a one-to-one correspondence with the set of observable states. This means that the observer is not able to distinguish all fundamental states of the system. Mathematically, this is described by taking the quotient of the ontological state space with respect to observational indistinguishability.

As a result, ontological states are partitioned into equivalence classes, each corresponding to a single observable state. This quotient construction naturally induces a probabilistic structure in the sense of Kolmogorov, where probabilities are determined by the normalized cardinalities of the corresponding classes. This is analogous to statistical mechanics, where a macrostate is defined by a set of microstates.

An important role is played by the cyclic structure of the ontological dynamics: shifts along a cycle do not change the probabilities of observable states and thus define a gauge degree of freedom analogous to the phase symmetry $U(1)$.

Two levels of time arise in the model. Ontological time parametrizes motion along a cycle and describes the sequence of fundamental states. Physical time is associated with the evolution of probability distributions on the quotient space. Thus, each moment of physical time corresponds to a class of indistinguishable moments of ontological time, which naturally introduces the notion of hidden time.

Within the proposed framework, quantum-like behaviour emerges as a result of taking the quotient of a deterministic dynamics at a deeper level of description.

The paper is organized as follows.

- Section 2 defines the ontological path space and introduces deterministic cyclic dynamics.
- Sections 3–4 construct the quotient mapping and derive the induced probabilistic structure, including the Born rule.
- Section 5 shows that the edge space of a complete graph $E \cong Z_p \times Z_p$ realizes a discrete phase space with an action of the Heisenberg–Weyl group.
- Section 6 derives the Klein–Gordon equation.
- Section 7 analyzes the Hong–Ou–Mandel effect.

The conclusion discusses conceptual implications and possible directions for further development.

Ontological Space

Consider a symmetric directed graph with loops

$$G = (V, E), \quad (2.1)$$

where $V = \{v_1, \dots, v_n\}$ is a finite set of vertices and $E \subset V \times V$ is the set of directed edges. The vertices V are interpreted as states of an internal observer (hereafter referred to as observable states). The edges: $E = \{e_1, \dots, e_n\}$ are interpreted as transitions between observable states. The set of edges E is regarded as a generating set (analogous to a basis) for the path space. The graph serves as the kinematical arena on which discrete processes are realized. The space formed by the vertices

corresponds to the physical (observable) level, whereas the space formed by the edges corresponds to the ontological (hidden) level of reality.

For definiteness, we assume that for every pair of vertices $\{u, v\} \in V \times V$ there exist two directed edges (u, v) and (v, u) . The graph is assumed to be fixed and is treated as the ontological structure of the model. Each path ξ represents a collection of transitions (edges) and is interpreted as an elementary discrete process.

The model assumes determinism at the ontological level. That is, the edges of the graph are rigidly associated with time. Since the fundamental dynamics defines a canonical ordering on the set of edges E , every element $\xi \in \mathcal{X}$ inherits this ordering and may therefore be regarded as an ordered set. In the representation

$$\mathcal{X} \cong \mathbb{B}^{|E|},$$

such ordered sets are naturally interpreted as vectors of a Boolean semimodule.

Since the ordering of elements is determined by ontological time, every element $\xi \in \mathcal{X}$ represents an ordered subset of edges and may be interpreted as a subpath of the global ontological cycle. Therefore, the elements $\xi \in \mathcal{X}$ will hereafter be referred to as path vectors:

$$\xi = \bigoplus_{e_i \in \xi} e_i, \quad (2.2)$$

Where $\bigoplus \cong \cup$ is the idempotent set-union operation.

The path space $\mathcal{X} = \mathcal{P}(E) \cong \mathbb{B}^{|E|}$ forms an idempotent semimodule over the Boolean semiring

$$\mathbb{B} = (\{0,1\}, \bigoplus, \cap), \quad (2.3)$$

with

$$\mathcal{X} := \mathcal{P}(E) = \{\xi \mid \xi \subset E\}.$$

An algebraic structure in which the operation \bigoplus is idempotent corresponds to the standard notion of an idempotent semiring [5].

We define an inner product as the cardinality of the intersection of two paths:

$$\langle \xi_1, \xi_2 \rangle := |\xi_1 \cap \xi_2|. \quad (2.4)$$

It is symmetric and positive-definite, but not bilinear in the sense of vector spaces over a field.

We define the norm of a path vector as

$$\|\xi\| := \sqrt{|\xi|}. \quad (2.5)$$

Since $\|\xi\| \notin \mathbb{Z}_2$, the norm is understood in a restricted functional sense: it is a mapping whose square returns the number of nonzero components of the path vector,

$$\|\xi\|^2 = |\xi| = \sum_{e \in E} \xi_e.$$

It is important to emphasize that $\|\cdot\|$ is not a norm in the linear-algebraic sense, since the space is not a vector space. Rather, it is a counting function introduced solely to ensure consistency with the probabilistic interpretation at the subsequent meta-level of description (see below).

Dynamics on the Ontological Space

Consider an admissible path $\xi \in \mathcal{X}_{adm}$, representing a simple edge cycle. Such a cycle can be defined as a mapping:

$$\xi(\tau) \in E, \quad \tau \in Z_N, \quad (2.7)$$

where $N = |\xi|$ is the length of the cycle, equal to the number of its edges. Due to the determinism of the ontological dynamics, evolution is given by a cyclic shift in the parameter $\tau \in Z_N$ which we refer to as ontological time:

$$\xi(\tau + 1) = U\xi(\tau), \quad (2.8)$$

where U is the cyclic shift operator implementing a permutation of the elements of the cycle. Thus, the dynamics at the ontological level is described by the action of an operator $U : E \rightarrow E$, which is a bijection on the set of edges. In the coordinate representation, the operator U is given by a permutation matrix.

Let us represent an edge (ontological) cycle in the form of an idempotent “superposition”:

$$\xi = \bigoplus_{\tau} \xi(\tau), \quad \text{where } \xi(\tau) \in E. \quad (2.9)$$

It is assumed that the basis $\xi(\tau)$ is ordered according to the sequence of edges in the cycle. Note that, while in quantum mechanics the components of a superposition coexist simultaneously, ontological states exist at different moments of ontological time. Therefore, the idempotent “superposition” should be understood as a dynamical process.

It is crucial that the requirement of determinism in the path space automatically leads to the requirement of preserving the scalar product (2.4). The operator U , being an element of the symmetric group of permutations, possesses precisely the required properties: it preserves both the norm and the scalar product, since it is an isometry with respect to the scalar product defined on \mathcal{X}

$$|U\xi| = |\xi|, \quad (2.10)$$

$$\langle U\xi_1, U\xi_2 \rangle = |U\xi_1 \cap U\xi_2| = |\xi_1 \cap \xi_2| = \langle \xi_1, \xi_2 \rangle. \quad (2.11)$$

Such evolution on the Boolean module is analogous to unitary evolution in a Hilbert space.

The assumptions of finiteness of the graph and determinism of the dynamics restrict the topology of admissible paths to simple cycles in the edge space (“edge determinism”). We define admissible paths $\mathcal{X}_{adm} \subset \mathcal{X}$ as simple edge cycles (each edge appears in the cycle only once). In contrast, paths in the vertex space may self-intersect.

The latter implies that, despite the strict determinism of the vertex dynamics induced by the ontological edge dynamics, the transition dynamics appears stochastic to an internal observer limited by incompleteness. It is important to emphasize that the observed dynamics does not merely appear random, but is genuinely random, since it is determined by the limitation of incompleteness (see Introduction), which implies that such an observer lacks information about the causes of transitions between states.

Factorization of Ontological Time

Consider the cycle (2.7). Since the observer, by definition, distinguishes only observable states—i.e., vertices $v \in V$ —the moments of ontological time at which the cycle passes through the same vertex are indistinguishable to the observer. This means that each “tick” of physical time may contain several hidden “ticks” of ontological time. Such a temporal structure induces the equivalence relation:

$$\tau_i \sim \tau_j \Leftrightarrow v(\tau_i) = v(\tau_j). \quad (3.1)$$

For each vertex $v \in V$, an equivalence class arises:

$$T_v = \{\tau \in \mathbb{Z}_N \mid v(\tau) = v\}. \quad (3.2)$$

The cardinality $|T_v|$ is equal to the number of returns of the system to the vertex v during one full ontological cycle. The quotient with respect to the equivalence relation (3.1) is defined as

$$\pi: \mathbb{Z}_N \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_N / \sim. \quad (3.3)$$

Here N is the length of the ontological cycle. Each class T_v collapses to a single point of observable (physical) time:

$$t = \pi(\tau). \quad (3.4)$$

This mapping “glues together” all moments of hidden time corresponding to the same observable state, so that after taking the quotient, information about the hidden time τ is lost. What remains is the multiplicity of visits K_v as a function of physical time t . For each vertex $v \in V$, the observed cycle is characterized by the visitation multiplicity:

$$K_v(t) = |T_v|_t \quad (3.5)$$

Here $|T_v|_t$ denotes the number of elements in the class T_v , i.e., the number of hidden time ticks during which the system resides in the state v . All these moments are indistinguishable for the internal observer and correspond to the same moment of physical time t .

The fraction of hidden time that the system spends in the state v naturally defines a probability measure for that state:

$$P_v = \frac{|T_v|}{N}, \quad \sum P_v = 1. \quad (3.6)$$

Origin of the Born Rule

The problem of the Born rule is usually regarded as a central aspect of the measurement problem, pointing to the absence of a theoretical mechanism explaining why the squared modulus of the wavefunction amplitude should be interpreted by the observer as a classical probability. In our case, this problem does not arise, since at the ontological level—which we consider as the foundation of quantum mechanics—there are no amplitudes.

In the preceding sections, we arrived at the conjecture that quantum mechanics on a complex Hilbert space is, most likely, an effective description induced by an ontological deterministic dynamics on an

idempotent semimodule. The mechanism in question is fundamental and is related to the limitations of incompleteness for an internal observer (see above). It is precisely this limitation that gives rise to a probabilistic description at the level of measurement.

The structure of the proposed model is fully consistent with Kolmogorov's axiomatic theory of probability. Let us identify the set of edges E with the space of elementary outcomes (atomic events) in the sense of Kolmogorov: $\Omega := E$. Then the corresponding σ -algebra is

$\mathcal{F} := \mathcal{X} = \mathcal{P}(E)$, Where $\mathcal{P}(E)$ is the power set of the set of edges. The probability space has the canonical form [6]:

$$\mathcal{S} \cong (\Omega, \mathcal{F}, P_\nu). \quad (4.1)$$

Here P_ν is the induced probability measure (3.6), defined in Section 3.

Thus, the probability space \mathcal{S} can be identified with the simplex of probability distributions. It satisfies all the axioms of a probability measure in the sense of Kolmogorov: non-negativity, normalization, and additivity.

Therefore, the probabilistic description does not arise as a fundamental postulate, but as a consequence of taking the quotient of a deterministic dynamics on the graph. In what follows, we show how one can establish a "matching" between the ontological level of description and the representational level provided by the formalism of quantum mechanics. For this purpose, we turn to a projective model of the quotient of the ontological space.

5.1 Graph Geometry of Phase Space

In this section, we show that the space of oriented edges of a complete graph with vertex set $V = Z_p$ naturally acquires the structure of a discrete phase space on which the Heisenberg–Weyl group acts. Each oriented edge connecting vertices $x, x' \in V$ is given by an ordered pair $(x, x') \in V \times V$. Thus, the edge space forms a discrete torus:

$$E \simeq Z_p \times Z_p. \quad (5.1)$$

We interpret the pair (x, x') as an elementary act of evolution: x is the observable coordinate, while x' is the next position, which is not directly observable but is objectively defined. In this sense, the space E plays the role of the ontological state space of the system.

Consider subsets of E defined by linear relations:

$$x' = rx + c \pmod{p}, \quad (5.2)$$

where $r, c \in Z_p$. These subsets represent discrete geodesics on the torus E (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1

Fixing the slope r , we obtain a family of parallel geodesics parametrized by c . The slope

$$r = \frac{x'}{x}, \quad x \neq 0, \quad (5.3)$$

defines a projective class:

$$[x: x'] \sim [1: r], \quad (5.4)$$

and thereby determines a point on the projective line $P^1(F_p)$. This corresponds to the standard definition of a projective space over a finite field [7].

Thus, the space of geodesics is naturally identified with a projective space, which we interpret as the space of momentum states. For a fixed r , the quantity

$$c = x' - rx \quad (5.5)$$

is invariant along each geodesic. Therefore, the set of parallel geodesics with a given slope r forms an equivalence class with respect to the transformations:

$$(x, x') \mapsto (x, x' + c). \quad (5.6)$$

These classes possess a natural affine structure and can be interpreted as orbits of the additive group Z_p . Thus, the space E is foliated into families of geodesics parametrized by the projective coordinate r and the affine parameter c .

5.2 Transition to a Dual Description

The correspondence

$$(x, x') \leftrightarrow (x, r), \quad r = \frac{x'}{x}, \quad x \neq 0 \quad (5.7)$$

is well defined on the affine part of the projective space $P^1(F_p)$. In this representation, the parameter $r \in F_p$, which characterizes the slope of geodesics on the torus, can be naturally interpreted as momentum, being a spatial frequency:

$$k = \frac{2\pi r}{p}, \quad (5.8)$$

Taking into account the isomorphism between the additive group \mathbb{Z}_p and the multiplicative group of p -th roots of unity, each orbit (5.2) can be represented as a complex function on the finite Hilbert space $\mathcal{H} = \mathbb{C}^p$:

$$\psi_k(x) = \sqrt{P_k} \cdot e^{-ikx} \quad (5.9)$$

Here P_k is the probability of finding the system in the momentum state $\psi_k(x)$. In the case of a complete symmetric graph, the amplitudes are uniformly distributed, and $P_k = 1/p$, where $p = \dim(\mathcal{H})$. In the general case, the amplitudes $|\psi_k(x)|^2$ are determined by the cardinalities of the affine classes (5.6), i.e., by the number of orbits with a given slope.

It is important to emphasize that the amplitude representation is not introduced as an additional postulate. Rather, it arises as the only way to embed the probabilistic structure of the quotient space into a complex linear space compatible with the spectral structure induced by the cyclic dynamics.

We assume completeness of the description of dynamics on the ontological space $\{x, x'\}$. From the correspondence (5.7), it follows that the dynamics on the corresponding phase space $\{x, k\}$ is also complete. Therefore, the dual representations complement each other, forming a complete ontological description, while the corresponding variables turn out to be mutually hidden. In particular, in the coordinate representation, the hidden parameter is momentum.

In this sense, Bohr's principle of complementarity acquires a constructive geometric interpretation: complementary variables arise as projections of a single ontological space onto different quotient spaces.

5.3 Emergence of the Heisenberg–Weyl Group

In Section 5.2 (see (5.7) and (5.8)), we passed from the edge space $(x, x') \in \mathbb{Z}_p \times \mathbb{Z}_p$ to the isomorphic (in the affine part) phase space $(x, k) \in \mathbb{Z}_p \times \tilde{\mathbb{Z}}_p$, on which shift operators act naturally. In the Hilbert space $\mathcal{H} = \mathbb{C}^p$, these transformations are implemented by operators X and Z :

$$(x, k) \mapsto (x + 1, k) \implies X\psi(x) = \psi(x + 1), \quad (5.10)$$

$$(x, k) \mapsto \left(x, k + \frac{2\pi}{p}\right) \implies Z\psi(x) = \omega^x \psi(x). \quad (5.11)$$

Here $\omega = e^{2\pi i/p}$. The operator X implements a shift in the coordinate x , while Z corresponds to a phase change associated with translation in momentum space. All combinations of these operators generate a finite-dimensional representation of the Heisenberg–Weyl group [8]. These operators satisfy the commutation relation:

$$ZX = \omega XZ, \quad (5.12)$$

which is a discrete analogue of the canonical commutation relation $[\hat{x}, \hat{p}] = i\hbar I$. Thus, the noncommutative algebra of quantum observables naturally arises from the geometry of translations in the discrete phase space associated with the edge structure of the graph.

The relation (5.12) can be written in the form of a group commutator:

$$X^{-1}Z^{-1}ZX = \omega \quad (5.13)$$

This means that traversing an elementary cell of the phase space $\mathbb{Z}_N \times \widetilde{\mathbb{Z}}_N$ along a closed loop depends on the orientation and results in a nontrivial global phase $\omega = \exp(2\pi i/p)$, which serves as a discrete analogue of a quantum geometric phase. An analogue of the quantum of action in this model is given by:

$$\hbar_{model} \cong \frac{1}{p} \quad (5.14)$$

Since noncommutativity is determined by the phase factor ω arising from traversing an elementary contour, this quantity naturally plays the role of a discrete analogue of the elementary symplectic area of the phase space.

Thus, the canonical commutation relation arises as a consequence of the geometry of translations on the discrete torus, rather than being postulated.

Derivation of the Klein–Gordon Equation

The ontology under consideration is discrete and defined on a finite graph and the associated torus $Z_p \times Z_p$. We now consider the continuum limit $p \rightarrow \infty$.

In this limit, discrete differences are approximated by derivatives, and the dynamics can be described in terms of smooth fields. Accordingly, the equations presented below should be understood as effective, arising after coarse-graining.

At the ontological level, the parameter τ plays the role of the trajectory length. For simplicity, consider a flat torus with metric $g_{ik} = \delta_{ik}$. The eikonal equation then takes the form:

$$(\partial_x \tau)^2 + (\partial_h \tau)^2 = 1. \quad (6.1)$$

To pass to a field description, introduce a scalar function $\xi(x, h, \tau)$, whose level surfaces are orthogonal to the trajectories. This leads to the relation:

$$\partial_i \tau = \frac{\partial_i \xi}{\partial_\tau \xi}, \quad i = (x, h). \quad (6.2)$$

Substituting (6.2) into (6.1), we obtain:

$$(\partial_x \xi)^2 + (\partial_h \xi)^2 = (\partial_\tau \xi)^2 \quad (6.3)$$

This equation corresponds to the relativistic eikonal equation in a space with an additional dimension (h). Thus, Lorentz invariance emerges as a consequence of the geometric structure of the ontological space.

For a plane wave $\xi(x, h, \tau) = e^{i(k_x x + k_h h - \omega \tau)}$ equation (6.3) yields the dispersion relation:

$$\omega^2 = k_x^2 + k_h^2. \quad (6.4)$$

Identifying $E \sim \omega$, $p \sim k_x$, $m = k_h$, we recover the familiar relativistic relation:

$$E^2 = p^2 + m^2.$$

Thus, the relativistic dispersion relation arises directly from the geometry of the ontological space. The dispersion relation can be written in operator form as:

$$\hat{\omega}^2 = \hat{k}_x^2 + \hat{k}_h^2. \quad (6.5)$$

Here: $\hat{k}_x = -i\partial_x$, $\hat{k}_h = -i\partial_h$, are the generators of the Heisenberg–Weyl group (see Section 5), while temporal evolution is determined by the operator: $\hat{\omega} = i\partial_\tau$.

Substituting these operators into (6.5), we obtain the linear wave equation:

$$(\partial_x^2 + \partial_h^2 - \partial_\tau^2)\xi = 0. \quad (6.6)$$

To derive the Klein–Gordon equation, we perform a separation of variables:

$$\xi(x, h, \tau) = \psi_x(x, \tau)e^{ik_h h}. \quad (6.7)$$

We assume that the observable field $\psi_x(x, \tau)$ does not depend on the hidden coordinate h , i.e.,

$$\partial_h \psi_x = 0. \quad (6.8)$$

This is the so-called cylinder condition. In the context of the present model, it may be interpreted as an analytical expression of subjective incompleteness.

Substituting (6.7) into (6.6) and taking (6.8) into account, we obtain:

$$\partial_\tau^2 \psi_x - \partial_x^2 \psi_x + k_h^2 \psi_x = 0. \quad (6.9)$$

This equation coincides with the one-dimensional Klein–Gordon equation, where the hidden coordinate h appears as an effective mass parameter $m = k_h$. Thus, mass emerges as a consequence of an additional cyclic degree of freedom of the ontological space.

Hong–Ou–Mandel Effect [9] in the Graph Model

In this section, we show that the constructed ontological model reproduces second-order interference—in particular, the Hong–Ou–Mandel effect—without introducing complex amplitudes and without postulating bosonic symmetrization. The suppression of coincidences arises as a consequence of the combinatorial structure of admissible ontological cycles.

Consider a directed graph:

$$G = (V, E), \quad V = \{1,2,3,4\}, \quad (7.1)$$

where:

- vertices 1 and 2 are input ports,
- vertices 3 and 4 are output ports,
- transitions between 1 and 2, as well as between 3 and 4, are absent,
- all other directed transitions are allowed.

Thus, interaction is possible only between input and output ports. The graph is not complete, reflecting the physical structure of a 50/50 beam splitter. Figure 2a shows the optical setup, and Fig. 2b shows the corresponding graph.

Fig. 2

On this graph, there exist four Eulerian cycles:

$$\begin{aligned}
 |L\rangle_1 &= (1,3,1,4,2,3,2,4), \\
 |L\rangle_2 &= (1,3,2,4,2,3,1,4), \\
 |L\rangle_3 &= (1,3,2,3,1,4,2,4), \\
 |L\rangle_4 &= (1,4,2,3,1,3,2,4).
 \end{aligned} \quad (7.2)$$

Each cycle passes through all admissible edges exactly once. The cycle length is 8, which allows one to naturally associate a full traversal with a phase 2π . Accordingly, an elementary step along the cycle corresponds to a phase increment

$$\Delta\phi = \frac{2\pi}{8}. \quad (7.3)$$

It is known that Pegg and Barnett, in studying the phase operator problem [10], proposed replacing the infinite-dimensional Hilbert space with a finite one. In this approach, a Fock state possesses a phase symmetry with step $2\pi/n$.

In our model, a two-photon state is represented as two indistinguishable excitations placed on the same ontological cycle with a relative phase shift

$$\Delta\phi = \frac{2\pi}{2} = \pi. \quad (7.4)$$

Thus, a biphoton corresponds to two points on the cycle separated by four steps. Evolution on the beam splitter is described by the shift operator:

$$|\psi\rangle_{\text{out}} = \hat{U}|\psi\rangle_{\text{in}}, \quad (7.5)$$

where \hat{U} implements a cyclic shift of the state by one step.

Case 1: Input state $|1, 1\rangle_{1,2}$

Consider the cycle $|L\rangle_1$. There exist exactly two admissible ways to place two photons at vertices 1 and 2 with a phase difference π . Under the action of the operator \hat{U} , both configurations lead to the following outputs:

- either both photons appear in port 3,
- or both photons appear in port 4.

There are no configurations leading to coincidence events (3,4). Therefore,

$$P_{3,4}(1,1) = 0. \quad (7.6)$$

Thus, a 100% suppression of coincidences is observed.

In the quantum formalism, this corresponds to the field transformation at the beam splitter:

$$|1,1\rangle_{1,2} \rightarrow \frac{|2,0\rangle_{3,4} + |0,2\rangle_{3,4}}{\sqrt{2}}. \quad (7.7)$$

In the present model, the suppression of coincidences arises not from destructive interference of amplitudes, but from the absence of admissible ontological cycles realizing coincidence events.

Case 2: Input state $|2, 0\rangle_{1,2}$ or $|0, 2\rangle_{1,2}$

Consider the cycles $|L\rangle_3$ and $|L\rangle_4$. These cycles correspond to configurations in which both photons enter through the same input port (with relative phase π).

In this case, under the action of the operator \hat{U} , the photons always separate and exit through different output ports. Therefore,

$$P_{3,4}(1,1) = 1. \quad (7.8)$$

This corresponds to the field transformation:

$$\frac{|2,0\rangle_{1,2} + |0,2\rangle_{1,2}}{\sqrt{2}} \rightarrow |1,1\rangle_{3,4}. \quad (7.9)$$

Thus, full cross-correlation is observed.

In the proposed model, second-order interference has a combinatorial-topological nature: the HOM effect arises as a structural property of the space of admissible processes, rather than as a consequence of the addition of complex amplitudes.

Thus, the model provides a nontrivial consistency check and may be regarded as a characteristic feature of a quantum theory.

Discussion and Conclusions

The paper considers the hypothesis that quantum mechanics is a description of reality from the perspective of an internal observer, that is, an observer who is simultaneously both the subject and the object of observation. Without claiming generality, we construct a simple model that demonstrates the emergence of quantum mechanics within such a self-referential structure.

In this work, we propose a discrete deterministic ontology that is assumed to underlie quantum mechanics. This construction is not intended to replace the standard formalism of quantum mechanics, but rather to clarify a number of well-known conceptual issues, including the meaning of the wavefunction, the measurement problem (the role of the observer), the problem of quantum phase, and the nature of randomness.

The model is based on the principle of subjective incompleteness—the inability of an observer (a subject), who is part of an isolated system, to distinguish all its states. As a result, the reality observed by the subject is partitioned into equivalence classes of ontological states that are indistinguishable to the observer. These classes are identified with physical states.

Since ontological time is associated with changes of ontological states, time in the model acquires the same quotient structure: each moment of physical time (i.e., the time that appears as a parameter in the equations of physical processes) corresponds to a class of ontological moments that are indistinguishable to the internal observer. We refer to this as hidden time. The classes of indistinguishable ontological “microstates” induce a probability measure. Therefore, the observed dynamics manifests itself exclusively as an evolution of probability distributions over observable states.

There is a clear analogy with statistical mechanics, where probability is determined by the number of microstates realizing a given macrostate. In our model, physical states (macrostates) correspond to cycles of ontological states (microstates). Shifts along an ontological cycle in ontological time do not change the observable physical state and therefore define a gauge degree of freedom (analogous to phase symmetry $U(1)$ in the continuous case).

Randomness in the model is not fundamental, but arises as a consequence of the incompleteness of the internal observer’s description of the dynamics. This mechanism, which is implicitly contained in the formalism of quantum mechanics, sheds light on the origin of the Born rule.

Approaches close in spirit to the one proposed here include deterministic reconstructions of quantum mechanics by ’t Hooft [11] and Stoica [12]. In ’t Hooft’s cellular automaton models, quantum behavior is assumed to emerge from deterministic dynamics. In our view, the limited success of these models is due to an underestimation of the role of the observer in finite models, without which it is impossible to obtain incompleteness—the main source of quantum behavior in the model.

In this context, Stoica's model (Stoica, 2025) appears more promising. However, despite the formal elegance of deriving the Born rule via classical measure theory using nonseparable Hilbert spaces, it raises serious concerns from the standpoint of physical interpretation. The transition to an uncountable basis and the introduction of a specific measure density $L^2(X, \mu)$ appear more as an *ad hoc* mathematical construction than as a fundamental explanation. In this case, nonseparability effectively serves as an infinite reservoir from which any desired measure can be obtained.

A formalization of the concept of "subjective incompleteness" is only possible within finite discrete models, since for uncountable sets there exists a bijection between a set (the set of ontological states of the system) and its proper subset (the set of observer states). Assuming that the origin of quantum behaviour is rooted in incompleteness, one may conclude that quantum mechanics is based on finite algebraic structures, while the conventional continuum-based formalism represents their smooth approximation.

Complex amplitudes and the Hilbert space structure thus appear not as fundamental entities, but as convenient representational tools arising from an embedding of the probability simplex into an amplitude space.

It is well known that the formalism of quantum mechanics employs the complex field primarily as a convenient mathematical carrier, while physical (observable) operations effectively reduce to structures in which only modulus-related quantities are essential. In the computation of probabilities, only quantities related to squared moduli of amplitudes contribute, whereas information about global phases remains unobservable.

In a number of modern works (e.g., Litvinov, Speyer, Sturmfels, and others) [13,14], idempotent semirings are used to transfer the formalism of quantum mechanics into the context of tropical geometry and to solve specific applied problems. However, these approaches typically do not aim to explain the fundamental structure of quantum theory.

The idempotent structure used in this work is formally related to algebraic constructions arising in Maslov dequantization [15]. However, in contrast to the latter—where idempotency appears as a classical limit of quantum theory as $\hbar \rightarrow 0$, in the present model, idempotent algebra is treated as ontologically primary and is not interpreted as a limiting case of quantum dynamics.

Thus, the standard formalism of quantum mechanics can be interpreted as an effective description arising from the transition from a deterministic cyclic ontology to a quotient space of observable states.

An important consequence of the proposed model is the natural emergence of nonlocal correlations. Ontological deterministic dynamics, unfolding in ontological time and inaccessible to the internal observer, manifests in physical time in the form of nonlocal correlations. In this way, quantum nonlocal realism acquires a justification without abandoning determinism at the ontological level.

The model is consistent with relational and participatory interpretations of quantum mechanics. It is also compatible with many-worlds-type interpretations (MWI), allowing for an alternative topological interpretation of branching structure in terms of cyclic ontological dynamics. A detailed analysis of this aspect lies beyond the scope of the present work.

Several directions for further research remain open, including a systematic classification of admissible graphs, extension of the model to multipartite systems, and analysis of symmetry and locality constraints. The present construction should not be regarded as a complete physical theory, but rather as a research program in which graph ontology defines the kinematic structure of the state space.

Thus, the proposed model provides a constructive and conceptually transparent path from deterministic discrete dynamics to quantum-like probabilistic behavior, which arises as a projective manifestation of a deeper ontological dynamics, thereby formalizing the configurational role of the observer in the structure of physical reality.

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